

COMPREHENSIVE KNOWLEDGE-GUIDED ASSESSMENT OF SKIN LESION-BASED CANCER DETECTION**Aakanksha Sahu**aakanksha99sahu@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Skin cancer is considered as one of the scariest and most life-threatening forms of cancer. Unrepaired deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) in skin cells results in genetic flaws or mutations on the skin, which is the cause of skin cancer. Early detection of skin cancer symptoms is necessary due to the rising incidence of the disease, its high death rate, and the high cost of treatment. Additionally, because of artifacts, low contrast, and similar representations like a mole, scar, etc., it can be difficult to distinguish skin cancer from a skin lesion. Therefore, techniques for lesion detection for accuracy, efficiency, and performance criteria are used to automatically detect skin lesions. The aim of this systematic review is to analyze studies focused on skin cancer image detection and classification. It also evaluates the effectiveness of these methods in real-world clinical environments. So in this paper we carried out a thorough search of the literature from different research papers only 15 papers that concentrated on creating, putting into practice, and validating methods to identify, diagnose, and categorize skin cancer in clinical settings were examined and targeted by the search. Descriptive analysis, data scenarios, data processing and procedures, study findings and viewpoints, and physician participation, diversity, and accessibility are all included in this review.

Keywords:

Skin Lesion, Dermoscopy, Melanoma, Deep Neural Network, Dense Net

INTRODUCTION

Compared to other cancer kinds, the number of patients with skin cancer is rising annually, according to recent surveys. In all this types Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC), Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC), Melanoma Merkel Cell Carcinoma, Kaposi Sarcoma, Cutaneous Lymphom, out of that Melanoma is a very common type of skin cancer which develops by melanocytes, the pigment-producing cells of the skin[8]. It has several cell types that contribute to the darkening of the skin. It is more deadly and harmful due to its quick spread. Although melanoma primarily develops on the back of a person's lower limb, it can occur elsewhere on the human body. By identifying skin cancer early on, it is possible to lower risk factors for the disease in individuals.

The need for initial examinations and the identification of various forms of skin cancer in order to stop it from getting worse and offer a better prognosis. Clinical professionals typically use visual details inspection, which has a low level of precision, to identify melanoma. Dermatologists can identify traits that are undetectable to the human eye by using dermoscopy, a non-invasive procedure that can produce a high-resolution image of the skin[10].

Several meta-analyses have demonstrated that, in comparison to the naked eye inspection, dermoscopy will improve and increase the accuracy of melanoma diagnosis[10]. In the hands of an inexperienced clinician, however, this method would lead to subpar performance. In addition, even professionals would find this

activity time-consuming and very subjective, as it relies on their judgment, which could result in differing diagnostic outcomes. Dermatologists find it extremely difficult to distinguish between benign skin lesions and malignant skin tumors due to their similar visual characteristics[16]. Even with highly qualified dermatologists and clinicians, the average reported sensitivity for melanoma diagnosis is frequently less than 80%.

The review study offers a current evaluation of how well AI algorithms function in the diagnosis and categorization of skin cancer[9]. It also explores the difficulties these systems encounter as well as potential future developments to improve dermatologists' diagnostic skills with AI assistance.

Examining research on the identification, categorization, and assessment of skin cancer photographs in a clinical context is the goal of this systematic review[3]. To do this, it is necessary to identify the primary strategies and difficulties that arise throughout the implementation of these tactics. This systematic review's significance stems from its capacity to compile and carefully analyze all relevant research in this area, providing a detailed understanding of the topic[2]. Researchers can then evaluate the caliber and reliability of previous research, pinpoint knowledge gaps, and suggest novel lines of inquiry. Additionally, physicians and other healthcare professionals wishing to utilize AI's ability to help with the diagnosis and treatment of skin conditions will benefit greatly from the knowledge this systematic review offers.

Challenges of skin lesion detection

Variations in picture kinds and sources are the cause of the challenges in identifying skin lesions. The appearance of human skin color varies greatly, making skin identification a challenging and intricate task[12]. These can be seen in Fig. 1 which is described below. The following highlights some of the difficulties posed by the intricate visual features of skin lesions images.

Fig. 1 Challenges of skin lesion detection: a. hair artefact, b. ruler mark artefact, c. low contrast, d. color illumination, e. bubbles, f. irregular boundaries, g. blood vessels, h. frame artefact

- Low contrast Low contrast from nearby tissues can also be present, which presents further challenges. Accurately segmenting the lesion is challenging due to the poor contrast between the lesion area and the surrounding skin.
- Color, texture, light beams, and the skin lesion's reflections can all have an impact on the illumination of dermoscopic images, producing multiresolution pictures.
- Various sizes and shapes Accurately identifying skin lesions is very challenging due to the wide variances among them, which also add complexity to these images. The location, size, and shape of lesions vary greatly.[22] For accurate analysis, the majority of image analysis approaches for skin lesion images necessitate first doing image pre-processing.

Related Dermoscopy Works

The clear skin lesion spot can be obtained using dermoscopy techniques, which then improve the optical appearance by eliminating reflection. However, automatic skin lesion identification contains some challenging tasks, like low contrast, skin color, hairs [veins, and similar visuals of melanoma and non-melanoma as well as artifacts. Pre-processing procedures can reduce all of this. To determine the accurate location of the skin lesion, in which pre-processed image is segmented.

There are still some gaps even though a dermatologist use a variety of dermoscopy techniques, such as the ABCDE rule, CASH, Menzies, and the 7-Points checklist, to detect melanoma[20]. First of all, a dermatologist's manual detection method using dermoscopic imaging is laborious and slow. Second, because there is little difference between normal and lesion skin, the results are occasionally inaccurate

For reliable findings, these dermoscopic images must undergo a number of preprocessing processes. Therefore, there are numerous computer-aided algorithms for automated melanoma identification from dermoscopic images in order to address the efficiency and accuracy[21]. Reviewing the best elements utilized in a computer-aided system for accurate skin cancer and melanoma diagnosis will be the main goal of this article.

Fig 2 Clinical Diagnostics Methods

In the above figure defines the normal clinical diagnostics methods which are use for detection and required methods find that manually detecting through dermoscopic imaging is a laborious and slow procedure. The limited contrast between normal and lesion skin can occasionally lead to inaccurate results[20].

LITERATURE SURVEY

A number of academics have suggested methods based on image processing to identify the many kinds of skin conditions. The initial step in this systematic review was to define the review framework[16]. The systematic literature review was conducted according to a general plan. Skin cancer detection has been the subject of

extensive research in an effort to help medical practitioners identify the disease early on. However, recent studies have concentrated on creating various artificial intelligence systems to automatically diagnose various forms of skin cancer.

Here, we provide a brief overview of several techniques reported in the existing literature.

Table 1 Defines the survey of different research papers

Authors	Techniques	Description	Result
Nawal Soliman[1]	Image Processing and Machine Learning	Technique works with color picture inputs and uses digital photographs of diseases that affect the skin area to determine the type of disease through image analysis. Multiclass SVM is used to categorize the features after they have been extracted using a trained CNN.	The technology has a 100% accuracy rate in identifying three distinct skin disease types.
Shunichi Jinnai et.al [4]	Deep learning-based categorization method for skin lesions with pigmentation ranging from brown to black.	Using the training dataset, we trained a faster, region-based CNN (FRCNN), and we evaluated the model's performance using the test dataset.	By their method of FRCNN for the research they got the Accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity was 91.5%, 83.3%, and 94.5%
Mehwish Dildar et.al[3]	A Review Using Deep Learning Techniques	Their review concentrated on the classification of lesion images using ANNs, CNNs, KNNs, and RBFNs. Every algorithm has benefits and drawbacks. The key to the best outcomes is choosing the classification method correctly. However, because CNN is more closely tied to computer vision than other neural network types, it performs better when classifying picture data.	For easier comprehension, research findings are displayed using tools, graphs, tables, methodologies, and frameworks.
Rehan Ashraf[5]	Region-of-Interest Based Transfer Learning Assisted Framework	ROIs are extracted from the images using an enhanced k-mean technique. Since the system is trained using images that exclusively include melanoma cells, these ROI-based methods aid in the identification of discriminative features. For ROI pictures from the DermIS and DermQuest datasets, we further employ a transfer learning model based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with data augmentation.	Accuracy came for their suggested method of the system was 97.9% for DermIS and 97.4% for DermQuest, each.

Khalid M. Hosny[6]	Classification of skin lesions using transfer learning and augmentation with Alex-net	In addition to 10-fold cross-validation for MED-NODE and DermIS—DermQuest, the training and testing dataset from ISIC has been used to refine the suggested DCNN weights. Their proposed approach is evaluated and compared with existing methods by using accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and precision metrics.	The accuracy percentages attained by this method are 96.86%, 97.70%, and 95.91%, respectively.
Philipp Tschandl[7]	Human-computer collaboration for skin cancer recognition	When it comes to clinical decision-making, high-quality AI-based help increases diagnostic accuracy more than either AI or physicians alone, and the least experienced clinicians benefit the most from AI-based support.	the total frequency of accurate diagnoses rose from 55.2% to 59.1% (mean difference of 3.7%, 95% CI 2.4% to 5.3%).
Vidya M[9]	Machine Learning Techniques	Textural characteristics were extracted using GLCM and HOG. The collected features are sent straight to classifiers, which use several machine learning algorithms like SVM, KNN, and the Naïve Bayes classifier to distinguish between benign and malignant skin lesions.	Using a SVM classifiers, the classification result of their project was 97.8% accurate with an area under the curve follows of 0.94. Additionally, using KNN, the sensitivity and specificity were 86.2% and 85%, respectively.
Adekanmi Adegun[12]	Deep learning techniques for skin lesion analysis and melanoma cancer detection	sought to offer a current survey that would help researchers create effective algorithms that can reliably and automatically identify melanoma from photos of skin lesions.	better classification performance, preprocessing methods like grab-cut and deep learning segmentation approaches are advised because they have been demonstrated to work exceptionally well.
Mohammad Ali	Applied a deep	odels that help forecast skin	On Datasets Test

Kadampur[15]	learning model architecture in cloud and classified dermal cell images	cancer more accurately are created using model-driven architecture in the cloud, which incorporates deep learning techniques into its fundamental implementations. The work provides an example of how to construct models and use them to categorize photos of dermal cells.	was done through the deep learning models and had developed the value of area under the curve is 99.77%.
Amirreza Rezvantalab[14]	For their Skin Cancer Classification they Used Different Deep Learning and Convolutional Neural Networks Algorithms	Eight diagnostic categories were included in their dataset which was used: dermatofibroma, vascular lesions, benign keratosis, actinic keratosis and intraepithelial carcinoma, melanoma, melanocytotic nevi, basal cell carcinoma, and atypical nevi. Comparing deep learning's capabilities with those of highly skilled dermatologists is the goal. All deep learning models fared better than dermatologists (at least 11%), according to the average findings.	For overall classification, DenseNet 201 had the greatest macro and micro averaged AUC values (98.16% and 98.79%, respectively).
MaryamTahir[13]	DSCC_Net: Multi-Classification Deep Learning Models for Diagnosing of Skin Cancer Using Dermoscopic Images	suggests a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based deep learning-based skin cancer classification network (DSCC_Net), which is applied to three publicly accessible benchmark datasets.	In their research project work they secured 94.17% of accuracy, 93.76% of recall, 94.28% of precision, and 93.93% of F1-score, through DSCC_Net and achieved 99.43% of AUC.
Qurrat Ul Ain,[11]	Generating Knowledge-guided Discriminative Features Using Genetic Programming for Melanoma Detection	To pick a single sort of features at terminals in a single tree of the GP person, genetic operators like crossover and mutation are created appropriately. Using two datasets of skin photos taken from various modalities, the effectiveness of the suggested approach is evaluated and contrasted with six popular classification algorithms, the standard (single-tree) wrapper technique, and embedded GP method.	This method's drawback is that it requires a binary mask, which is often supplied by a qualified dermatologist, in addition to the pictures. Grayscale and color features with both local and global information have been incorporated in the suggested strategy.

			Prior to using feature selection and feature construction, GP will also be utilized for feature extraction.
Marco Stiven Sastoque Mahecha[17]	Design of a System for Melanoma Detection Through the Processing of Clinical Images Using Artificial Neural Network	One of the most advanced methods for early identification of Melanoma as a preventative measure is mages analysis. One of the numerous developed methods for digitally processing photos and detecting characteristic similarities is artificial neural networks.	76.67% accuracy rate, a 78.79% success rate in situations involving melanoma, and a 74.07% success rate in cases involving benign tumors.
Irfan Ali Kandhro[19]	Performance evaluation of E-VGG19 model: Enhancing real-time skin cancer detection and classification	features are entered into machine learning techniques like Linear Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Logistic Regression (LR), and Support Vector Machine (SVM), our findings show that the overall classification accuracy for skin cancer detection and classification is greatly increased when the E-VGG19 model is combined with conventional classifiers.	potential to significantly influence healthcare, especially in the area of dermatology, the incorporation of real-time capabilities into the system to enable instantaneous skin cancer diagnosis offers an attractive route for future research.
Kunjie Yu[18]	AGenetic Programming Approach with Adaptive Region Detection to Skin Cancer Image Classification	suggested GP approach offers a thorough description of skin photos by automatically and adaptably extracting useful local and global features from various input image sources. To choose the lesion locations from skin photos for feature extraction, a novel region detection function has been created.	Three assignments involving the classification of skin cancer images were used to test GP. In the majority of cases, the ARDGP methodology produced performance that was either noticeably superior or comparable to nine benchmark methods.

			Additional investigation confirmed that our parameter settings were effective.
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METHODOLOGY

This section represents the systematic literature review in relation to skin lesion-based cancer detection is presented in this section. There were five main stages to the evaluation process i.e Identification, Selection, Eligibility, Data Extraction and Synthesis

Identification: Search was carried out across key databases to find pertinent papers, focusing on studies that used knowledge-guided or AI-based methods for automated skin lesion analysis and classification. Studies that included steps like image preparation, feature extraction, and computationally based skin condition categorization were given priority under the inclusion criteria.

Fig 3 Basic Work Flow of Skin Lesion

Above figure 3 illustrates a typical workflow in skin lesion classification, including image input, preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification into conditions like eczema, melanoma, psoriasis, and healthy skin, as followed in many reviewed studies.

Selection: At this point, the titles and abstracts of every article that was obtained were examined to determine how relevant they were to knowledge-guided skin lesion-based cancer diagnosis. Papers that were duplicates, written in languages other than English, or that had little methodological detail or had nothing to do with image-based analysis were not included. For full-text review, only peer-reviewed publications that clearly applied classification algorithms and skin disease datasets were kept.

Eligibility: We evaluated by the chosen studies of quality and applicability. To ascertain eligibility, We separately examined (19)each article's title and abstract.

The following standards were applied:

- The abstract clearly outlines the goals, methods, and findings.
- The study focuses on skin cancer computer-aided diagnostic methods, especially in actual clinical settings.
- It provides performance indicators for AI-based systems, including specificity, sensitivity, and accuracy.

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- The diagnostic model's creation and/or validation procedure is explained in detail.
- A critical analysis of the findings is included in the report, pointing out the drawbacks and possible biases of AI-based techniques.

Data Extraction: Relevant information was methodically retrieved and arranged using a consistent form from every study that qualified. The data that was extracted comprised: Source, authors, year of publication, and study title. Details of the dataset (annotations, image modality, size, and kind) Methodology (classification algorithms, feature extraction, model architecture, and picture preprocessing)

- The kind of AI or knowledge-based methods that are employed. Performance indicators (such as F1-score, AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy).
- Procedures for clinical relevance and validation.
- Important conclusions, restrictions, and identified biases
- Two authors independently examined every piece of data to make sure it was accurate and consistent. Agreement and discussion which was there used to be settle in disagreements.

Synthesis: Our study's ending phase includes data synthesis, which was broken down into two crucial parts. First, we systematically examined the unprocessed data that was acquired during the literature review procedure. We then assembled metadata related to the selected publications for our literature evaluation.

RESULT

Table 1, research demonstrates the benefits of new developments in machine learning and image analysis for the detection, categorization, and assessment of skin cancer applications. processing, detecting cancerous or skin lesion with excellent sensitivity and specificity. Additionally, for groups with limited access to dermatologists, mobile applications provide an accessible method of screening. It is crucial to remember that even while all of the strategies included in Table 3 exhibit encouraging outcomes, many of them are still in the testing and clinical validation stages. Therefore, before thinking about the broad and successful application of these approaches in medical practice, it is imperative to continue thorough evaluations and rigorous study, as stressed by numerous researchers. Although these developments have the potential to completely transform the early detection and diagnosis of skin cancer, it is crucial to ensure their clinical relevance and dependability through thorough research. Lastly, it is critical to guarantee that AI applications are created and evaluated in an ethical and responsible manner. This involves protecting the privacy of patient data and security, in addition to guaranteeing openness in the algorithm creation and training procedures

CONCLUSION

In this systematic review Several neural network methods for the detection and classification of skin cancer have been covered in this systematic review article. These methods are all non-invasive. Multiple steps are necessary for the identification of skin cancer, including preprocessing, image segmentation, feature extraction, and classification.

This study emphasizes how numerous studies are significantly advancing deep learning, pattern recognition, and image processing skills. These developments allow for quick and precise analyses, which may result in diagnosis in real time. This development increases the likelihood of a cure and reduces the need for invasive procedures by assisting in the early detection of skin cancer.

In conclusion, we surveyed the methodologies and different technologies from other research areas and presented a framework on skin cancer detection which help to analyse which methodology is better with accuracy and precision. In future we implement our system with Artificial Techniques so that it can easily modify with real time data and execute it fast without any noise and disturbance

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